

APPLICATION OF VIRTUAL REALITY TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION. INTRODUCTION OF VIRTUAL REALITY TECHNOLOGY IN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the analysis of the use of virtual reality technology in various educational fields in the world and in Azerbaijan. A comparative table is provided, which indicates the main possibilities of using the considered technology in teaching various scientific disciplines: natural, technical, social, and humanitarian.

Keywords: virtual reality, virtual museum, visualization, education.

Virtual reality (VR) today is a relatively young technology, which is gradually being used in many areas of life. The VR industry is rapidly developing, which is apparently due to its widespread use in many industries, such as medicine, architecture, computer science, psychology, and education. In this regard, there are many definitions of this concept. The following, introduced by Fuchs and Bishop in 1992: VR is real-time interactive graphics with 3D models, combined with a display technology that gives the user immersion in the model world and direct manipulation.¹

In other words, VR is a fundamentally new way of visualization and interaction between a person and a computer, which creates a virtual space, with the possibility of subsequent interaction.

The virtual reality device includes a virtual reality helmet, headphones, motion sensors, or manipulators.

The computer generates a virtual space in which a person navigates and interacts through the following senses: sight, hearing, and touch. This is the basic principle of the idea of using virtual reality, which is as follows:²

1) The user should have a feeling of immersion in the virtual world;

2) The user must interact with the objects of the virtual world;

3) The user is able to explore the virtual world to the same extent if he were part of the world.

The main advantages of this technology, according to the article on the use of VR in education, are³,

firstly, the complete immersion of a person in an interactive environment, due to which the concentration of attention occurs and, consequently, the quality of perception of the material increases, as well as the possibility of interacting with recreated objects.

Thus, by using VR technology in the education process, teachers have the opportunity not only to visualize the studied phenomena, processes, and objects but also to teach how to interact with them. So, for example, the training for aircraft pilots is conducted in a computer-generated environment, which makes it possible to prepare pilots for work without risk to life and avoids high financial costs⁴; Conducting medical practice, including surgical work, allows you to gain primary work experience without the participation of living people, which prevents harm to patients⁵; in mathematics, the application of technology allows the visualization of geometric objects and algebraic equations, which contributes to a deeper understanding of the material.

Today, due to the intensive development of educational Internet platforms, as well as the improvement of VR, technology is being integrated into the learning process. Numerous studies show that virtual reality technology increases the degree of motivation and interest of students. In addition, the possibility of immersion in the environment and the ability to interact with objects is of great importance - thus, students are able to better understand and remember the material being studied.

¹ «The Past, Present, and Future of Virtual and Augmented Reality Research: A Network and Cluster Analysis of the Literature» *Front. Psychol.*, 06 November 2018

Sec. Human-Media Interaction

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02086>

² VIRTUAL REALITY AS A TOOL IN THE EDUCATION Sandra Dutra Piovesan¹, Liliana Maria Passerino¹ and Adriana Soares Pereira² ¹ Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul ² Universidade Federal de Santa Maria

³ «Immersive VR and Education: Embodied Design Principles That Include Gesture and Hand Controls» Mina C. Johnson-Glenberg*

⁴ How Virtual and Augmented Reality Are Used in Aviation Training and Other Use Cases

Michael Velichko

⁵ Virtual reality and the transformation of medical education

Jack Pottle, co-founder and chief medical officerA

SCIENTIFIC DIRECTION	THE OPPORTUNITY THAT VR PROVIDES
SPACE, ITS STRUCTURE, AND DEVELOPMENT	Virtual museums with the possibility of observing astronomical processes. The study of planets, stars, galaxies, their structure, and location in the universe ⁶ . The concept of gravity with the ability to control the time and speed of processes ⁷ .
EARTH SCIENCES	The study of the landscape, the structure of the earth's crust, and soil. The possibility of recreating natural processes and the results of their impact on the environment. The study of flora and fauna. The study of climatic zones and their features ⁸ .
SCIENCES ABOUT PHYSICAL, CHEMICAL, AND BIOLOGICAL PROCESSES	Conducting experiments without harm to health, visualization of the molecular structure of substances, as well as the processes occurring in them. ⁹
HUMANS AS A BIOLOGICAL SPECIES	The structure of the body, the work of internal organs. ¹⁰
THE MEDICINE	Conducting medical practice without the participation of living people. ¹¹
MATHEMATICS	Visualization of algebraic equations, geometric shapes, and functions. ¹²
HISTORY	Virtual museums. ¹³

Thus, speaking about the main advantages of virtual reality, the visualization should be highlighted: the reconstruction of object models and virtual museums.

In Azerbaijan, the gradual introduction of virtual reality technology into the educational process is starting, which has not yet become widespread and takes place only in specialized courses, as an experimental technology¹⁴: as an example, the Virtual Museum project dedicated to art objects can be cited¹⁵. In addition, there are courses that prepare teachers to conduct classes using augmented and virtual reality technologies¹⁶. However, for full implementation in the learning process, it is necessary to develop programs and methods, as well as train relevant specialists.

Summing up, we can say that virtual reality really takes place in teaching, as it greatly simplifies the process of visualization and understanding of the material. It should be noted that without prior thorough preparation, the use of this technology can lead to certain difficulties, so it is necessary to conduct intensive scientific work on the development of methods and training, as well as writing special programs.

References

1. «The Past, Present, and Future of Virtual and Augmented Reality Research: A Network and Cluster Analysis of the Literature» *Front. Psychol.*, 06 November 2018 Sec. Human-Media Interaction <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02086>

⁶ «Virtual Reality Applied to Astronomy Education in Primary and Middle School» Part of the Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering book series (LNEE, volume 551)

⁷ «THE APPLICATION OF VIRTUAL REALITY IN ASTRONOMY EDUCATION» Wernhuar Tarnq National Hsinchu University of Education

⁸ Applying Virtual Reality Technology to Geoscience Classrooms Sukonmeth JITMAHANTAKULI BASE STAR, Chulalongkorn University, THAILAND Piyaphong CHENRAI2 BASE STAR, Chulalongkorn University, THAILAND

⁹ The Use of Virtual Reality in A Chemistry Lab and Its Impact on Students' SelfEfficacy, Interest, Self-Concept and Laboratory Anxiety Almer Gungor 1*, Denise Kool 2, May Lee 2, Lucy Avraamidou 2*, Niek Eisink 2, Bauke Albada 3, Koos van der Kolk 4, Moniek Tromp 2, Johannes Hendrik Bitter

¹⁰ Can virtual reality improve traditional anatomy education programmes? A mixed-methods study on the use of a 3D skull model

Shi Chen, Jiawei Zhu, Cheng Cheng, Zhouxian Pan, Lingshan Liu, Jianhua Du, Xinhua Shen, Zhen Shen, Huijuan Zhu, Jihai Liu, Hua Yang, Chao Ma & Hui Pan

¹¹ Virtual Reality in Medical Education Ahmet B. Ustun <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1640-4291> Bartin University, Turkey Ramazan Yilmaz Bartin University, Turkey Fatma Gizem Karaoglan Yilmaz Bartin University, Turkey

¹² February 1, 2019, 9 min, Vol. 76, No. 5 "I Can See It!": Math Understanding Through Virtual Reality

¹³ <https://storytogo.ca/classroom/course/immersive-experiences-in-natural-and-cultural-history/lessons/virtual-reality-vr-in-natural-cultural-history-education/>

¹⁴ Проект, который изменит мир: охват STEAM в Азербайджане стремительно растет Наила Аббасова 4 апреля 2022, 14:12

¹⁵ <https://citylife.az/content/ru/11602/-vystavka-zapolnennaya-pustota-iskusstvo-virtualnoj-realnosti> Выставка "Заполненная пустота: искусство виртуальной реальности"

¹⁶ <https://www.edtech.az/page/tehsilde-artirilmis-ve-virtual-realliq-tetbiqetmelimeri-telimi>

2. «Immersive VR and Education: Embodied Design Principles That Include Gesture and Hand Controls» Mina C. Johnson-Glenberg*

3. VIRTUAL REALITY AS A TOOL IN THE EDUCATION Sandra Dutra Piovesan¹, Liliana Maria Passerino¹ and Adriana Soares Pereira² ¹ Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul ² Universidade Federal de Santa Maria

4. How Virtual and Augmented Reality Are Used in Aviation Training and Other Use Cases Michael Velichko

5. Virtual reality and the transformation of medical education Jack Pottle, co-founder and chief medical officer A

6. «THE APPLICATION OF VIRTUAL REALITY IN ASTRONOMY EDUCATION» Wernhuar Tarn National Hsinchu University of Education

7. «Virtual Reality Applied to Astronomy Education in Primary and Middle School» Part of the Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering book series (LNEE, volume 551)

8. Applying Virtual Reality Technology to Geoscience Classrooms Sukonmeth JITMAHANTAKUL¹ BASE STAR, Chulalongkorn University, THAILAND Piyaphong CHENRAI² BASE STAR, Chulalongkorn University, THAILAND

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12. February 1, 2019, 9 min, Vol. 76, No. 5 "I Can See It!": Math Understanding Through Virtual Reality

13. <https://storytogo.ca/classroom/course/immersive-experiences-in-natural-and-cultural-history/lessons/virtual-reality-vr-in-natural-cultural-history-education/>

14. Проект, который изменит мир: охват STEAM в Азербайджане стремительно растет На иля Аббасова 4 апреля 2022.

15. <https://citylife.az/content/ru/11602/-vystavka-zapolnennaya-pustota-iskusstvo-virtualnoj-realnosti> Выставка "Заполненная пустота: искусство виртуальной реальности"

16. <https://www.edtech.az/page/tehsilde-artirilmis-ve-virtual-realliq-tetbiqetmeleri-telimi>

ДИНАМІКА ВИТІКАННЯ РІДИНИ ІЗ ЄМНОСТЕЙ КЛАСИЧНИХ ГЕОМЕТРИЧНИХ ФОРМ. ЧАСТИНА ІІ.

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DYNAMICS OF LIQUID OUTFLOW FROM CONTAINERS OF CLASSIC GEOMETRIC SHAPES. PART II

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Анотація

Досліджена динаміка витоку рідини при виливанні через край методом повороту ємностей певних класичних геометричних форм з постійною кутовою швидкістю відносно закріпленої точки або фіксованої осі. Знайдено закон зміни розходу рідини в залежності від кута нахилу. Врахування отриманих результатів дає змогу корегувати роботу поворотних механізмів так, щоб вилив рідини був рівномірним, що є важливим при виливанні у форми.

Abstract

The dynamics of the liquid flow during overflow over the edge by the method of rotation of containers of some classic geometric shapes with a constant angular velocity relative to a fixed point or a fixed axis were studied. The law of change of liquid consumption depending on the angle of inclination was found. The results obtained make it possible to correct the uniformity of pouring liquid into molds.